

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
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JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

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THE USE OF AGRICULTURAL TERMINOLOGIES IN RUSSIAN

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

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